

Monastery of Our Lady of Saydnaya

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The Monastery dedicated to Virgin Mary, the mother of Jesus Christ, is situated 30 km to the north of the city of Damascus in Syria, in the mountains that overlook the city of Saydnaya. It belongs to the Greek Orthodox Patriarchate of Antioch and it operates as a female monastery. It possessed the famous icon of the Virgin of Saydnaya, also known as the Shaghoura (meaning “the renowned” or “the illustrious” in Syriac), attributed to the hand of Saint Luke the Evangelist. It is believed that the convent was founded by the Byzantine emperor Justinian in 547, following two visions he has had of the Mother of God. The first indicated her request to have a church built for her as well as the intended site, while the second provided details for the convent’s architectural design. The church was dedicated on September 8, the day of the Virgin’s Nativity, which is still the day on which the Monastery of Saydnaya celebrates. However, there is no factual evidence supporting that Justinian founded it. Moreover, its walls bear no traces of a 6th-century construction, whereas Procopius of Caesarea († 561), the official historian of Justinian, does not mention the foundation of the convent. Instead, historical records mention that the convent was founded by a widow of Damascus during the Byzantine period, who withdrew in the desert to lead an ascetic life in Qalamoun. In either case, the origin of the convent is quite uncertain. Information about the Monastery’s history is sparse. It is assumed that unlike many churches destroyed in Syria and Egypt in 1014 by the Fatimid caliph al-Hakim bi-Amr-Allah, Saydnaya was most probably spared. The Monastery is first mentioned in a report addressed in 1175 to the emperor Frederick I Barbarossa by the Burchard of Strasbourg. The document describes Saydnaya and recounts its history. At the beginning of the 13th century it began to draw Western pilgrims in large numbers. Saydnaya was also spared by the Mamluk rulers (1250-1517), who destroyed many other churches and monasteries in the region. Saydnaya received financial support by the Tsar Ivan IV the Terrible (1560), while the Tsars continued to support it by authorising alms by Russian pilgrims. During its long history, the convent has undergone constant alterations, but the current structure belongs to the end of the Ottoman period and the early 20th century. Three sections of the complex, however, are older since they belong to the Medieval period: i. The Church of the Virgin, a small vaulted chapel at the south side of the apse of the 19th-century church that houses the miraculous icon of the Mother of God; ii. the lower floor, that includes the kitchen and the cellars, all of them barrel-vaulted at differing levels and connected by steps; and, iii. the long barrel-vaulted room below the cells of the nuns, built of alternating stones and brick, currently the visitors’ reception room. All three parts were built directly upon the bed-rock, which is visible in the passage leading to the Shaghoura. More recent renovation works have revealed that the present building was not constructed exactly on the foundations of the old one. Its central axis has been moved a few metres to the north. If there are any foundations left, the north side must be hidden underneath the church floor, while the south side might be buried below the garden between the 19th-century church and the south wall of the fortification.

Date Range: 547 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Saydnaya

Region tags: Syria

Saydnaya, 30 km to the north of the city of Damascus in Syria

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Hamilton, B. "Our Lady of Saidnaiya; an Orthodox Shrine Revered by Muslims and Knights Templar at the Time of the Crusades," R.N. Swanson. Vol. The Holy Land, Holy Lands, and Christian History. Woodbridge/Rochester, NY, 2000
- Source 2: Immerzeel, M. "The Monastery of Our Lady of Saydnaya and Its Icon," ECA, 4 (2007)
- Source 3: Devos, P. "Les Premières Versions Occidentales de La Légende de Saïdnaia," Analecta Bollandiana, 65 (1947)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://saidnaya.com/>
- Source 1 Description: Website of Saydnaya Monastery
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.antiochpatriarchate.org/en/page/our-lady-of-saydnaya-patriarchal-monastery/146/>
- Source 2 Description: Information about Saydnaya Monastery, website of the Greek Orthodox Patriarchate of Antioch

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation

Type of elevation

- Mountain

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- Yes

- ↳ Type of feature
 - Leveling of ground
 - Terracing
 - Trackway or road-surface
 - Water feature
 - Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - Yes

- ↳ The structure has a definite shape
 - Other [specify]: The Monastery has an oblong shape and is perched on a lofty rock overlooking the landscape below

- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]: The Monastery has many features such as cisterns, water channels etc.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The Monastery was destroyed and rebuilt during different periods of its history

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The Monastery was destroyed and rebuilt during different periods of its history

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: The Monastery still exists but in the past parts of it were severely damaged and rebuilt.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: However, this is a place for prayer and worship of God by Orthodox Christians.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Notes: However, the Monastery is dedicated to Virgin Mary, the Mother of God

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

– Private individual

– Other [specify]: It is believed that the convent was founded by the Byzantine emperor Justinian in 547. However, the walls bear no traces of a sixth-century construction, whereas Procopius of Caesarea († 561), the official historian of Justinian, does not mention the foundation of the convent. Instead, historical records mention that the convent was founded by a widow of Damascus during the Byzantine period, who withdrew in the desert to lead an ascetic life

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Revealed by other kind of supernatural being(s) [specify]: Virgin Mary, the mother of Christ

Notes: It is believed that the convent was founded by the Byzantine emperor Justinian in 547, following two visions of the Mother of God. The first indicated her request to have a church built for her and the intended site, while the second provided details for the convent's architectural design

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: It is believed that the convent was founded by the Byzantine emperor Justinian in 547, following two visions of the Mother of God. The first indicated her request to have a church built for her and the intended site, while the second provided details for the convent's architectural design.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Notes: It is believed that the convent was founded by the Byzantine emperor Justinian in 547, following two visions of the Mother of God. The first indicated her request to have a church built for her and the intended site, while the second provided details for the convent's architectural design

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The convent is built on a mountain

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery is a structure composed of smaller ones as well as various features

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The most important part of the Monastery is the main church and the space where the miraculous icon of the Virgin is kept

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Pigments, binding materials and glass tesserae for the mosaics, the latter being contemporary though

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Pigments and glass tesserae

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Mainly icons and the iconostasis, as well as other objects such as lamps

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ, the Son of God

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The Mother of God

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints, Prophets, the Mother of God

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

Notes: Animals are not the central subject of depictions. They may appear though in scenes that depict scenes from the life of Christ, the Virgin, of Saints etc.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The reliefs are strictly decorative

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

– Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Lives of Christ, Virgin Mary, the Saints and other

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: A mosaic at the entry of the Monastery depicts the vision of emperor Justinian, which has instigated the foundation of the Monastery of Saydnaya

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: At the entry of the Monastery there is a Deisis scene. It is though contemporary

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: A mosaic at the entry of the Monastery depicts the story of the foundation of the Monastery by emperor Justinian. It is though contemporary

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Both mosaic scenes are contemporary. There are no mosaics contemporary with the creation or later restoration phases of the Monastery

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions in Christian Orthodox monuments are present for informing about the person and event depicted

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Inscriptions in Christian Orthodox monuments are present for informing about the person and event depicted

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: Byzantine style

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels, cherubim and seraphim

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: Second Coming

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Cross, Dove and other

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Saints, Prophets, Apostles, the Mother of God, Jesus Christ

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the life of Christ, the Virgin and Saints

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the life of Christ, the Virgin and Saints

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Depiction of the believed founder of the Monastery, Justinian

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: However, the convent has a place dedicated to the burial of the nuns

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Humans visit though the place to pray and for pilgrimage to the icon of the Virgin

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Visitors come though to pray to the icon of the Mother of God

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Orthodox services

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Impossible to know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: The services are taking place daily

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Notes: There are no orthodoxy checks. However, the rituals and services follow the established liturgical order and typika

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Notes: There are no orthopraxy checks. However, the rituals and services follow the established liturgical order and typika

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings to the Monastery may vary from very simple things or objects like food to very valuable objects or lands

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings to the Monastery may vary from very simple things or objects like food to very valuable objects or lands

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

- Other [specify]: Material offerings to the Monastery may vary from very simple things or objects like food to very valuable objects, funds or lands

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

- No

Notes: It is not mandatory for pilgrims and visitors but it is for the nuns that live at the Monastery

Is maintenance of the place performed:

- Yes

↳ Is it required:

- Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

- No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

- Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

- Yes

Notes: The maintenance is performed both by the nuns and external specialists such as architects, archaeologists and other

↳ Other

- Other [specify]: The age and importance of the monument oblige its owners and governmental authorities to overlook and protect the Monastery

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

- Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

- optional (rare)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

- No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:
– No

Are festivals present:
– No

Notes: However, the Monastery celebrates on September 8, on the day of the Virgin's Nativity

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:
– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time
– Yes

Notes: The convent still operates today as a female Monastery

↳ Present part time
– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Female

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Notes: The nuns of the monastic community will most probably live there by the end of their life. However, there is no legal attachment per se with the place

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery has its Mother superior (higoumeni) and a council of nuns that takes decisions.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Monastic cells

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Experts from various fields and archaeologists

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Notes: Land and probably also goods produced there

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: There are no scriptures associated with the place. Yet, there are many pilgrimage accounts that mention it

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Monastery of Our Lady of Saydnaya, Immerzeel, M.. "The Monastery of Our Lady of Saydnaya and Its Icon", ECA, 4 (2007).

Reference: Monastery of Our Lady of Saydnaya, Devos, P.. "Les Premières Versions Occidentales De La Légende De Saïdnaia", *Analecta Bollandiana*, 65 (1947).

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